

Cascadia Region Earthquake Science Center

Partnerships & Applications Workshop June 27, 2024

Workshop Report

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Executive Summary

On June 27, 2024, CRESCENT convened its first annual Partnerships and Applications Workshop. A diverse group of participants were invited, providing opportunities for relationship development and bidirectional flow of information between research scientists and the community partners who apply earthquake hazard science to improve society's seismic resilience. Following a series of presentations by community members and CRESCENT scientists, breakout sessions highlighted the complexities surrounding regional seismic hazards and explored how CRESCENT's research products can best be applied in various sectors. By engaging representatives from state and federal agencies; urban, rural, and coastal communities; infrastructure and utilities sectors; and more, we sought to identify common challenges and areas for collaboration.

The responses and discussions from the meeting underscored a shared commitment to improving seismic hazard communication, resource allocation, and collaborative efforts. Participants expressed a clear need for accessible data, effective public engagement, and actionable hazard scenarios to enhance preparedness and response. The enthusiasm for stronger cross-organizational relationships and the development of user-friendly tools reflects a collective drive to connect scientific research with practical, impactful solutions. Moving forward, incorporating these insights and recommendations will be crucial in refining CRESCENT's research agenda and ensuring that its products meet the needs of diverse stakeholders in order to foster resilience throughout Cascadia.

Introduction

Seismic Hazard and Resilience in the Pacific Northwest

The Cascadia Subduction Zone (CSZ) is the primary seismic hazard for the USA and Canada, posing significant risks of fatalities, injuries, and infrastructure damage from earthquakes, tsunamis and associated cascading consequences (landslides, liquefaction, fire, etc.). National seismic models in both countries predict that a megathrust event will create strong shaking (MMI>6-7) across most population centers, and widespread tsunami inundation that will impact entire coastal towns and critical infrastructure.

While natural hazard awareness and attitudes towards resilience have certainly evolved over the last few decades, there is an acute need to develop the region’s “earthquake culture” to be ready for the imminent recurrence of a megathrust earthquake. As depicted in Figure 1, a well prepared, resilient society not only recovers faster from such a devastating event, but learns from the experience, adapts, and becomes more resilient.

Figure 1: Resilience Triangle

When a disaster strikes, a society with low resilience suffers large impacts, bounces back slowly, and often never recovers the level of services it had before the event (= a large ‘resilience triangle’). This is the potential situation across most of the Pacific Northwest today. Meanwhile a resilient society suffers fewer impacts and recovers quickly to an improved level of services (= a small resilience triangle, e.g. Japan). CRESCENT’s mission is for the center’s science and outreach to enable partners to carry out the necessary work to reduce the size of Cascadia’s resilience triangle.

CRESCENT Overview

The Cascadia Region Earthquake Science Center (CRESCENT) was funded by the National Science Foundation in 2023 as North America’s first subduction zone earthquake hazards center — conceived to respond to the urgent need for increased seismic resilience in the Pacific Northwest. The center is designed around three pillars (Figure 2), dedicated to its overarching goals.

Figure 2: CRESCENT Pillars and Major Activities

1. Science Pillar

Goal: develop a better foundational understanding of CSZ earthquakes and their associated hazards

This pillar contains the center’s cyberinfrastructure and five working groups (WGs), each tasked with generating community products, including: community velocity and fault models, dynamic rupture and earthquake cycle simulations, stress budget and coupling calculations, and paleoseismological databases. CRESCENT also supports four special interest groups (SIGs), focusing on emerging research frontiers and technologies in earthquake science.

2. Geoscience Education and Inclusion Pillar (GEI)

Goal: promote diversity in earth sciences and train the next generation of geoscientists to address the challenges presented by our dynamic planet.

GEI activities are based around collaborations with minority-serving institutions in the Pacific Northwest and national pedagogical institutions at the secondary, undergraduate, graduate, and postdoctoral levels. Major activities include research and training experiences and summer schools that create opportunities for students to participate in

subduction zone science, build skills essential to research, and position themselves for meaningful careers in science and related fields.

3. Partnerships & Applications Pillar (P&A)

Goal: facilitate collaboration between researchers in academia and those managing earthquake-related hazards in the Pacific Northwest, including federal, state and local government agencies, policy makers, practitioners, and the public at large.

This pillar is centered around developing and maintaining relationships between center scientists and targeted partners so that the science pillar products are relevant, applicable and ultimately contribute to improved regional earthquake hazard resilience. Leveraging existing networks and connectivity with related geohazard research initiatives (e.g. Pacific Northwest Seismic Network (PNSN), Cascadia Coastlines and Peoples (CoPes) hub, Cascadia Lifelines Program (CLiP) and Statewide California Earthquake Center (SCEC)), P&A's objectives require robust bidirectional communications through regular online and in person engagement opportunities. The annual P&A workshop is a key activity for this pillar.

Workshop Overview

Workshop Purpose, Goals and Design

CRESCENT's inaugural Partnerships and Applications Workshop on June 27, 2024 was designed to bring together representatives from communities concerned with Cascadia earthquake hazards resilience and research, including local, state and federal agencies, tribal organizations, emergency managers, utilities, industry, non-profits, and educational institutions. The one-day workshop was hosted on the University of Oregon campus at the White Stag building in downtown Portland, chosen for its central location and access to Cascadia's main urban centers via major roadways and the international airport.

The overall workshop goals were to:

1. Build community around Cascadia hazards research and risk mitigation;
2. Learn group's various needs as they relate to a better understanding of CSZ hazards;
3. Share updates on CRESCENT's currently funded research and seek input on the utility and application of the center's products; and
4. Identify opportunities and mechanisms for immediate and future inter-organizational collaboration.

The meeting was structured in three parts to address these goals (Appendix 1). Morning sessions consisted of a series of short talks and poster presentations showcasing the work

and perspectives of different organizations as they relate to the need for a better understanding of the CSZ. The morning session featured representatives from utilities and infrastructure companies, state and federal agencies, and local community organizations. These were followed by presentations on seismic hazard communication and outreach, and case studies of existing geohazards research and priorities for policy work in the region.

In the afternoon, members of the CRESCENT leadership team gave an overview of the center, and representatives from the science working groups and special interest groups gave lightning talks on their research objectives and progress to date. This gave context for the two facilitated breakout discussion sessions that followed.

In the first session, participants were asked to share the challenges faced by their organizations with respect to regional earthquake hazards and then to reflect on the interconnectedness of these challenges with the work of CRESCENT and other organizations present at the workshop (Appendix 3.1). The second session sought specific feedback on how CRESCENT's products could be most useful and accessible to the organizations present and asked participants to consider how the center can best facilitate ongoing interorganizational collaboration (Appendix 3.2). Breakout group facilitators captured their group's responses to both sessions on poster sheets that were displayed around the conference room wall. Participants were given time to review and comment on other group's summaries during two "gallery walks."

The meeting closed with an individual reflection activity in which participants shared their top learning from the day and expressed their main hope or excitement for work in this area going forward (Appendix 3.3).

Participation and Representation

There were 120 registrants for the workshop. An indication of representation is apparent from the post event survey in which 53 respondents reported their professional role and organization (Table 1).

Approximately one third of respondents identified as researchers with the other two thirds representing practitioner and educator roles. Approximately one third of respondents were from academic institutions, one third were from state/local agencies, and one fifth were from federal entities. Approximately one tenth of respondents represented each of utilities/industrial organizations and non-profits. During the day, several congressional staff from the Oregon and Washington legislature dropped by the workshop to hear presentations and connect with participants.

Table 1. Characteristics of Survey Respondents

Note: N = 53 responses

<p>What is your primary professional role? <i>(mark only one)</i></p>	<p>30% Emergency Management 26% Research Scientist 13% Engineering, architecture 8% Educator or Extension Specialist 4% Student 2% Technician, staff member 2% Planning, Zoning, Regulatory - Spatial Modeling - Post-doc 15% Other (specify): "Government relations" "policy/politics" "State network administrator" "Research, engineering" "Research and extension" "Outreach, Public Information" "Meteorologist" "NWS, NTHMP Administrator"</p>
<p>Which terms best describe your organization? <i>(mark all that apply)</i></p>	<p>38% State, regional or local agency 26% University offering related PhD degrees 23% Federal department, agency, or other federal entity 11% Nonprofit organization 8% Public utility 2% University offering related Masters (but not PhD) degrees 2% Private company or industry organization - Primarily undergraduate institution (PUI) - Minority-serving institution (MSI) - Historically Black College or University (HBCU) - Community College - High School or Middle School - Tribal organization 2% Other (specify): " I currently don't belong to any organization"</p>

Emergent Themes

Group discussions and individual reflection/evaluation responses revealed a unifying appreciation of the need for **inter-organizational coordination and collaboration** to address the scale of the hazards posed by the CSZ across such a vast geographical area (Appendix 3). Aligned with this overarching need, the priorities and recommendations recorded during the workshop can be categorized into four key themes:

A. SCIENCE COMMUNICATION AND ENGAGEMENT

Responses indicate a widespread need for clear and intentional communication of science and risks, and critical thinking about engagement with organizations and communities impacted by those risks. Unified messaging between information-producing organizations (federal and state agencies and academic institutions) is crucial to build trust with the communities using the information, who want clear, actionable steps for event preparation and response. Participants expressed desire for CRESCENT and agencies to: (i) reduce sensationalism in messaging, (ii) appropriately communicate hazard uncertainties, and (iii) disseminate science in plain, jargon-free language to serve multiple audiences.

B. EMERGENCY PREPAREDNESS AND RESPONSE PLANNING

It is clear from the workshop dialog that emergency planning and response must be better coordinated across geographic and organizational boundaries, from the local level (individuals/households/communities) to state, regional and national levels. In addition to the communication needs identified above, improved resilience in this area requires greater investment in critical infrastructure redundancy (i.e. power, water, waste, transportation and telecommunications) and development of localized post-event response plans that feed into state and federal level plans and exercises. Workshop participants expressed a desire for updated earthquake scenarios and inclusion of a multi-hazards approach in planning and training.

C. DATA AVAILABILITY AND ACCESS

Many responses mentioned the need for additional site, regional, and/or discipline-specific scientific data to support existing projects and resilience efforts. Others highlighted the desire for a centralized Cascadia data repository or “dashboard” and a call for data availability in multiple formats tailored for different end-users/applications. Participants affirmed the importance of CRESCENT’s goal to seek regular practitioner involvement in the product development process. They also stressed the need for release of products and results to be vetted and delivered by the appropriate agencies to avoid the spread of misinformation and possible loss of public confidence and trust.

D. RESOURCE LIMITATIONS

Participants reported challenges to seismic resilience efforts coming from lack of resources, including agency funding, allocation of human resources, hiring difficulties, and skills shortages. Additional complications noted were the need to produce cost-benefit analyses to justify projects and a pressure to prioritize preparedness efforts in a region facing multiple competing hazards (e.g. climate change, wildfire, cyber threats).

Next Steps

Many of the challenges and recommendations gathered during the workshop will require additional funding and resources beyond those allocated to CRESCENT in its current structure if they are to be addressed. Consequently, the next steps below and summarized in Table 2 include both action items that can be implemented immediately by the center, and some that are iterative, involving longer term coalition building and solicitation of support.

1. Interorganizational Coordination

→ **Continue to host an annual P&A Workshop:**

Feedback from workshop participants indicated that the P&A workshop was valuable beyond learning about CRESCENT – specifically, in that it served as a networking opportunity for representatives across disciplines, roles, and geographic borders. It seems that there are currently limited venues for such collaboration. These in-person meetings develop connections between groups and agencies, which is a key step toward meeting the overarching need for interorganizational coordination that spans the themes identified above. CRESCENT has set dates 26-27 June, 2025 at the UO Northeast Portland campus for the next annual P&A workshop.

→ **Ensure representation of partners in other CRESCENT activities:**

CRESCENT P&A can work with scientists to ensure inclusion of multi-disciplinary and resilience perspectives in the center’s programmed topical science workshops, Work Group/Special Interest Group meetings and town hall events, thus expanding the collaboration and networking opportunities offered by the center.

→ **Engage with tribal communities:**

The voices at the table inform definition of key societal needs and concerns; this is an important part of supporting resilience across communities, and with a social justice lens. In this vein, CRESCENT acknowledges the responsibility it holds to consider how the center’s science may impact tribal communities in the region and recognizes that tribes have not been well represented at events such as this workshop so far. CRESCENT P&A pillar is committed to intentional, long-term tribal

engagement through: (i) educating staff (P&A program staff are participating in Portland State University's 2025 Tribal Relations Certificate Program); (ii) working with a tribal consultant to define a formal tribal relations strategy; (iii) building relationships with local tribal organizations to enable future co-designed research.

2. Science Communication & Engagement

→ **Meet with technical/response agency partners:**

Direct, regular meetings with “technical” and “response agency” partners (organizations with research programs, seismic hazard assessment interests and/or public hazard communication responsibilities) are a tool to establish core science needs, identify and pursue intersections with CRESCENT research, and to establish trusted communications pathways and partners. These meetings will also help determine a feedback and vetting process for the development and release of CRESCENT's products and research.

→ **Establish science communication needs:**

CRESCENT P&A can facilitate conversations with partners related to their specific science communication needs and offer support and training for center scientists in science communication. This is important for producing unified messages about hazards and supporting hazard and planning agencies in maintaining the trust they have built with communities and constituents.

→ **Amplify partners in CRESCENT outreach:**

CRESCENT's quarterly newsletters and social media channels are an effective way to increase awareness of partners and their resilience efforts, promoting a culture of collaboration and potentially leading to future co-designed research opportunities. Specific features could include “partner profiles”, notices of technical partners' reports, data releases, or findings, and sharing of agency public preparedness messaging and initiatives.

3. Emergency Preparedness and Response

→ **Expand CLiP collaboration:**

CRESCENT currently supports the Cascadia Lifelines Program (CLiP) monthly webinar series run out of Oregon State University. These webinars are designed for practicing and researching engineers and policy makers, primarily concerned with Oregon's lifelines infrastructure but often relevant to resilience efforts across the Pacific Northwest. CRESCENT can continue to solicit and promote presentations for CLiP's webinar series, as well as pursue direct collaborations with CLiP member organizations and other regional lifelines providers.

→ **Establish scenario needs:**

CRESCENT can facilitate the discussion and potentially seed the planning of a scenario exercise in the CSZ. This is a complex project beyond the scope of the present center, though soliciting which scenario parameters to include or consider, and providing a roadmap for how entities could collaborate is an achievable and worthwhile first step. Building community and partner support in the short term, CRESCENT can work toward creating possible funding opportunities and longer-term plan execution.

4. Data availability and access

→ **Engage partners in CRESCENT cyberinfrastructure development:**

CRESCENT's cyberinfrastructure tools are a key interface for disseminating the center's data and products to both researchers and practitioners. It is critical that the tools be accessible to a wide range of audiences outside of the academic community and so the center should continue to hold open feedback periods during tool development, as well as seek specific reviews from technical partners.

→ **Explore the Cascadia "data dashboard" concept:**

Although not defined in CRESCENT's current work plan, a clear service to the Cascadia resilience community would be a centralized "data dashboard" for earthquake-related hazards, including access to (i) CRESCENT data and cloud-based tools, (ii) existing technical data from other agencies, and (iii) authoritative sources of information for hazard estimates and messaging. Contributing to this longer-term vision, CRESCENT can help identify the data gaps and specific datasets that are of consistent interest as the P&A pillar convenes and meets with partners.

5. Resource availability

→ **Promote CRESCENT seed grants:**

CRESCENT can contribute to resource limitations through disbursements from its annual seed grants program. In addition to the award itself, CRESCENT can work towards increasing access to funding through supportive actions including: advertising the program to diverse audiences, soliciting feedback from partners to define the annual Request For Proposal (RFP) priorities, and being available to support applications (e.g. answering questions, hosting meetings and information sessions, providing guidance on priorities and formats for grant writing).

→ **Promote CRESCENT GEI programs:**

CRESCENT can encourage and support partner participation in CRESCENT GEI programs focused on workforce development and skill building. These include the

undergraduate twinning program, and technical short courses. Increased partner engagement in these programs would expand the range of opportunities for participants, while potentially offering a direct pipeline to fill critical roles and skills gaps in the geosciences workforce.

→ **Seek and promote external funding opportunities:**

CRESCENT can share external funding opportunities (NSF, NEHRP, FEMA, etc.) with the community at large, and attempt to facilitate the pursuit of funds for co-designed research projects between center scientists, and regional communities, organizations, and agencies.

Table 2. Summary of emergent themes and next steps

<i>Emergent Themes/Needs</i>	<i>CRESCENT actions/next steps</i>
INTERORGANIZATIONAL COORDINATION Overarching need	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • function as a hub seeking intentional cross border/discipline representation at: annual P&A meeting, topical workshops, WG/SIG and sector-specific partner meetings
SCIENCE COMMUNICATION AND ENGAGEMENT unified messaging and plain language communication of earthquake science, hazards and uncertainties targeted to different audiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • regular technical/agency partner meetings for science updates and to establish trusted communications pathways to practitioners and public • workshop partner sci. comm. needs and identify training opportunities
EMERGENCY PREPAREDNESS & RESPONSE PLANNING wider infrastructure redundancy and unified response planning across borders and sectors of society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CLiP webinars to highlight infrastructure resilience developments • workshop scenario needs of emergency managers and planners
DATA AVAILABILITY AND ACCESS centralized, navigable data sets, tailored to applications/end users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • develop CRESCENT cyber tools under FAIR open science principles • seek regular beta testing and feedback from practitioners • establish data gaps and needs for specific partners/sectors
RESOURCE LIMITATIONS lack of funding, competing budget priorities, personnel and skill shortages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • promote CRESCENT Seed Grants and GEI initiatives • gain input from partners on priorities and skills gaps • share other funding opportunities with community

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Appendices

Appendix I – Workshop Agenda

Morning: Welcome & Presentations

- 8:30-9:00am | Registration and light breakfast
- 9:00-9:15am | Welcome and introduction to the workshop
- 9:15am-12:00pm | Community presentations: short talks and poster session
- 9:15-10:15am | Presentations Session 1
- 9.15 am – Cascadia Subduction Zone (CSZ) science & resilience needs: utilities and infrastructure
 - *Design of a new resilient water transmission system for the Cascadia Subduction Zone earthquake and other seismic hazards*, Mike Britch, Tualatin Valley Water District
 - *Importance of the Cascadia Subduction Zone for Pacific Gas & Electric Company assets*, Albert Kottke, Pacific Gas & Electric Company
 - *Updating BC Hydro’s 2012 PSHA model*, Martin Lawrence, BC Hydro
- 9.40 am – CSZ resilience planning (I): state and federal agency updates and needs
 - *Mapping, modeling, and communicating earthquake and tsunami hazards in Oregon*, Jonathan Allan and Lalo Guerrero, Oregon Department of Geology and Mineral Industries
 - *Toward actionable tsunami forecast for Cascadia*, Vasily Titov, NOAA Pacific Marine Environment Laboratory
 - *ODEM: Meet your state emergency management agency*, Althea Rizzo, Oregon Department of Emergency Management
 - *How science can support emergency management to inform planning for a CSZ event*, Hannah Rabinowitz, FEMA Region 10
- Session 1 Q+A
 - 10:15-10:45pm | Coffee and poster session
 - 10:45am-12:00pm | Presentations Session 2
- 10:45 am – CSZ resilience planning (II): local/community efforts and needs
 - *The Redwood Coast Tsunami Work Group: A collaborative approach to develop strategic messaging for Northwest California*, Ryan Aylward, NOAA National Weather Service
 - *Emergency management and vulnerability in low-income housing*, Carolina Gomez, Home Forward
 - *Use of earthquake science in disaster airlift planning*, Jim Origliosso, Oregon Disaster Airlift Response Team

- 11:10 am – CSZ hazard communication and outreach
 - *ShakeAlert: Earthquake early warning for all*, Gabriel Lotto and Robert de Groot, Pacific Northwest Seismic Network/USGS
 - *Assessment of experiences, interest, and accessibility associated with hazard warnings to improve equity in disaster risk reduction*, Mike Brudzinski, University of Miami, Ohio
 - *Three tips for engaging conversations between earthquake professionals and members of the public*, Marcie Benne, Oregon Museum of Science and Industry
- 11:30 am – CSZ science & resilience partnership case studies and call to action
 - *Introduction to the Cascadia CoPes Hub: geohazard research and community engagement*, Harold Tobin, University of Washington
 - *Oregon’s Top Two Danger Zones*, Yumei Wang, Portland State University
- Session 2 Q+A
 - 12:00-1:00pm | Lunch (provided)

Afternoon: CRESCENT Updates and Breakout Discussions

- 1:00-1:15pm | CRESCENT overview
- 1:15-1:50pm | CRESCENT working group and special interest group presentations
- Community Fault Model (CFM)
- Community Velocity Model (CVM)
- Cascadia Paleoseismology (CPAL)
- Dynamic rupture, Earthquake cycles and Tsunamis (DET)
- Coupling, Seismicity and Slow-slip (C3S)
- Special Interest Groups: Offshore Observations, Ground Motion Modeling, Ground Failure, Cascadia Fluids Model
 - 1:50-2:00pm | Breakout session introduction
 - 2:00-2:55pm | Breakout discussion 1 – CSZ organizational needs and concerns
 - 2:55-3:15pm | Refreshments
 - 3:15-4:00pm | Breakout discussion 2 – Application of CRESCENT products and ways to engage
 - 4:00-4:30pm | Breakout session review
 - 4:30-5:00pm | Closing comments and networking

Appendix 2 – Poster Presentations

#	Authors	Title
1	The CRESCENT Team	An Overview of the Cascadia Region Earthquake Science Center (CRESCENT)
2	Emily Hooft, et al.	Building a Community Velocity Model for the Cascadia Region and Beyond
3	Tina Dura, et al.	Introducing the Science Goals for the Cascadia Region Earthquake Science Center (CRESCENT) Cascadia Paleoseismology Working Group (CPAL)
4	Tina Dura, et al.	Catastrophic impacts of sudden coseismic subsidence and associated rapid sea-level rise during the next Cascadia subduction zone earthquake
5	Eric Dunham, et al.	The CRESCENT Dynamic Rupture, Earthquake Cycle, and Tsunamis Working Group (DET)
6	The CRESCENT Team	CRESCENT Community Fault Model (CFM)
7	The CRESCENT Team	Coupling, Seismicity and Slow-slip (C3S) Working Group
8	The CRESCENT Team	Special Interest Groups: Offshore Observations, Ground Motion Modeling, Ground Failure, and Cascadia Fluids Model Special Interest Groups (SIGs)
9	Alessandra Burgos	The Cascadia Coastlines and Peoples Hazards Research Hub (COPEs Hub)
10	Carrie Garrison-Laney	Washington Sea Grant's Coastal Hazards Resilience Team
11	Lori Dengler, et al.	The Redwood Coast Tsunami Work Group: Planning and Outreach on California's North Coast
12	Jonathan Allan, Lalo Guerrero	Oregon Department of Geology and Mineral Industries: A Partner for Investigating and Communicating Oregon's Geologic Hazards
13	Todd Becker, et al.	Assessment of Tsunami Risk and Exposure to California's Coastal Communities using FEMA's Hazus Tsunami Model and ESRI Demographic Data
14	Sean R. Santellanes, Diego Melgar	Remapping Tsunami Inundation Hazard Using Heterogeneous Sources
15	Yajie Lee, et al.	Towards Probabilistic Tsunami Risk Estimates Using Stochastic Earthquake Sources
16	Yong Wei, Carrie Garrison-Laney, Chris Moore, Clint Pells	Testing Crustal Fault Tsunami Sources in the Salish Sea: Comparing Modeled Inundation With the Geologic Record at Discovery Bay, WA
17	David W. Edgington	Planning for Earthquakes and Tsunamis: Lessons from Japan for British Columbia

18	Tianhaozhe Sun, et al.	Northern Cascadia Drilling: Establishing plate-scale borehole observatories to study how plate boundaries communicate
19	Gabriel Lotto, William Steele	Using ShakeAlert Earthquake Early Warning to Reduce Earthquake Losses
20	Carla Herrán, Marcie Benne, Robert de Groot, Jenny Crayne	Engage with your regional museums, parks, and libraries for community resilience
21	Michael R. Brudzinski, et al.	Examination of Usage Rates for the Multi-Hazards San Diego County Emergency App to Improve Earthquake Early Warning
22	Michael R. Brudzinski, et al.	Approaches to Multilingual Surveying on Hazard Awareness and Alerting to Improve Equity in Disaster Risk Reduction
23	Liz Safran, Erik Nilsen, Peter Drake, Bryan Sebok	Rehearsing Disaster: Earthquake Preparedness Behavior in an Interactive Environment
24	Amina Meselhe, Dan Cox, Dylan Sanderson, Jenna Tilt	Human-centered connectivity and transportation network recovery following a Cascadia Subduction Zone Earthquake and Tsunami
25	Ana Tijerina Esquino	Critical Energy Infrastructure Hub – Ongoing Research on Risks
26	Oregon Disaster Airlift Response Team (ODART)	ODART – An Aviation Resource to Assist Your Community (*tri-fold brochures)

Appendix 3 – Summary of Responses

This appendix includes (i) an analysis of the group responses from the two facilitated breakout discussion sessions, (ii) a summary of the individual responses gathered during the closing reflection activity, and (iii) a summary of feedback from the post-event survey.

A3.1 Breakout Session Responses

Breakout Session 1: Organizational concerns with relation to regional hazards and intersections with CRESCENT and other research groups

For the first breakout session, up to eight participants sat at tables organized by organizational affinities and primary areas of concern: state and federal agencies; rural, remote, and coastal communities; infrastructure; public outreach and communication; and tsunamis. Participants were asked two questions:

- *“What are the biggest challenges your organization faces with respect to the regional hazards of the Cascadia Subduction Zone?”*
- *“Where do these challenges intersect with the goals of a) CRESCENT as a whole, b) specific scientific working groups within CRESCENT, and/or c) other organizations that have presented today?”*

The first two columns of Table A1 show summarized responses from each group’s poster sheet for the first question, categorized by theme. Many groups ran out of time or were confused about what the second question was attempting to elicit, and, as a result, did not answer specifically. Useful feedback arose nonetheless; including the recommendations summarized in the third column of Table A1.

Breakout Session 2: Exploring partnership by understanding product applicability and opportunities for interorganizational collaboration

For the second breakout session, participants were separated into groups according to interest in the different CRESCENT working groups, special interest groups, the geoscience education and inclusion pillar, and nonspecific open discussion tables. Participants were asked two questions:

- *“In what ways can the products outlined by the CRESCENT working groups be made applicable and accessible to you and your organization?”*
- *“How can CRESCENT best facilitate interorganizational collaboration?”*

The first two columns of Table A2 show summarized responses from each group’s poster sheet for the first question, categorized by theme. As occurred with the first breakout session activity, fewer groups responded to the second question than the first and unifying themes were not apparent. Notable responses to this prompt are recorded in the third column of Table A2.

Table A1 – Summary of Breakout 1 responses

Theme	Challenge/need	Recommendations
<p>I. HAZARD AND RISK COMMUNICATION</p>	<p>addressing misinformation and managing mistrust of scientific and governmental entities</p> <p>ensuring that messaging is both consistent across agencies and accessible to diverse audiences</p> <p>conveying the severity of risks from seismic hazards without eliciting sensationalism</p> <p>appropriately communicating statistical uncertainty – balancing relating the science truthfully with mitigating public misunderstanding of statistical uncertainty</p> <p>translating scientific findings into actionable hazard response plans and language accessible by non-scientists</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • involve social scientists in translating scientific products into behavioral changes around hazard preparedness • include community-based emergency response teams and mutual aid organizations to event response planning • mitigate the impact of cultural biases on scientific models and disaster response plans by equitably engaging diverse communities • leverage connections to the Department of Defense and the Department of Energy for funding resilience programs and recovery efforts
<p>II. RESOURCE LIMITATIONS</p>	<p>effectively allocating limited financial and political resources to earthquake preparedness, particularly when balanced against other natural hazards such as wildfires, sea level rise, and adverse weather events</p> <p>competition between prioritization of “low-hanging fruit” projects and longer term, higher cost projects</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • host a data clearing house to provide centralized access to models, data, and other CRESCENT products
<p>III. DATA COLLECTION AND ACCESS</p>	<p>collecting and sharing high quality, easily accessible data related to seismic hazard research</p> <p>ensuring that this data is serviceable by a wide range of users with a wide range of technical expertise</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • serve as a facilitator for communication between academic research scientists, state and government agencies (e.g., DOGAMI, USGS), policy makers, utilities and infrastructure engineers, emergency managers, and community groups
<p>IV. INTERORGANIZATIONAL COLLABORATION</p>	<p>coordinating scientific research and practical application of that research across disparate organizations, from governmental agencies, academic institutions, community groups, and utilities and infrastructure</p>	

	<p>redundancy and inconsistency in communication both between relevant organizational entities and between those entities and the public</p>	
<p>V. HAZARD PREPAREDNESS AND RESPONSE</p>	<p>translating scientific findings into actionable hazard response plans in language accessible by non-scientists</p> <p>need for enhancing and coordinating community readiness and disaster resilience at different societal scales, from the preparedness of individual family units to the entire Cascadia region</p> <p>need to address vulnerabilities and increase redundancy in critical infrastructure – highest need in rural and coastal areas with large distances to response centers</p> <p>planning for different stages of event response and recovery and developing these plans effectively in conjunction with target communities</p> <p>preparing for cascading and compounding multi-hazard events and the possibility for temporally overlapping but unrelated hazards, such as heat waves or wildfires</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • fund and host additional workshops, including meetings similar to the inaugural PAC workshop as well as informational meetings to help non-technical workers understand earthquake and hazard science • produce seismic hazard maps in future iterations of CRESCENT and develop other tools/products that facilitate the identification of dominant seismic hazards in local areas • include crustal events and upper plate faults in addition to subduction-related events in seismic models and related messaging

Table A2 – Summary of Breakout 2 responses		
<i>Thematic needs</i>	<i>Recommendations</i>	<i>Ideas for interorganizational collaboration</i>
I. Accessible database for CRESCENT products	<p>CRESCENT products to be accessible to both technical and non-technical audiences</p> <p>Specific suggestions:</p> <p>a well-designed database viewer/dashboard</p> <p>downloadable tabulated data in multiple, easily transferable formats (e.g., 2D kml files, shapefiles, json, etc.)</p> <p>availability of data at different resolutions</p> <p>a clear process for integrating new data</p> <p>common metadata between different datasets</p> <p>all available within a single repository</p> <p>inbuilt consideration of dynamism for models like the CVM and CFM.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> involve and compensate community organizers in the planning of future meetings and change the location of meetings each year for the sake of accessibility host an annual “state of the CFM workshop” and have a standardized process for revising faults with a “changes” file to record reasons why a fault model was modified or removed from the CFM DOGAMI and Department of Natural Resources databases like the Vs30 measurements to inform shallow CVM properties. develop a cross-border collaborative earthquake catalogue between American and Canadian agencies that addresses Cascadian seismic risks, including episodic tremor and slip (ETS) phenomena
II. Effective public education, communication, and engagement	<p>clear, consistent messaging to the public incorporating minimal jargon, realistic visualizations, and educational materials</p> <p>Specific suggestions:</p> <p>utilize common software like Google Earth for visualization purposes</p> <p>harness AI to customize content delivery to specific audiences</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> collaborate with other research efforts to address spectral acceleration, peak ground velocity, duration of ground shaking, number of load cycles, and predominant periods, and include infrastructure representatives to ensure that this data is usable to them

	<p>provide technical summaries designed for different levels of expertise and including easily translatable sector-appropriate actions</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • collaborate with organizations that are closely nested within the community, such as libraries, museums, senior centers, climate activism groups, social justice groups, and other environmentally focused initiatives such as the Portland Harbor Superfund. • provide a forum for queries and open interactions, on a web-based platform like Slack and/or regular interactive settings like webinars and workshops, with an emphasis on non-academic participants
<p>III. Scenario-based outputs and products</p>	<p>couch CRESCENT products within a scenario framework that takes into account primary and secondary seismic hazards and the complex interactions between these hazards</p> <p>Specific suggestions:</p> <p>present scenario-based outputs to the public in a gamified format (e.g. augmented reality, smart phone apps) allowing for interactive practice of hazard drills</p> <p>scenarios could be incorporated into public forecast systems</p>	

A3.2 Reflection Activity Responses

In the closing session participants were asked to write anonymous responses to the following prompts on index cards that were collected at the end of the workshop (summarized in Table A3 and A4):

- “Something I learned today...”
- “After today, I am excited about....”

Table A3 – Summary of Reflection Activity prompt 1 responses	
<i>Main learning</i>	<i>Specific takeaways</i>
CRESCENT’s structure, activities, and contributions	clearer understanding of the organization, goals, and products of CRESCENT appreciation of the importance of aligning CRESCENT’s role with the expectations and needs of the varied groups interested in the seismic hazards of Cascadia
Trends in earthquake research and technology	enthusiasm for improved early warning systems for primary (e.g., ground rupture, infrastructure damage) and secondary impacts (e.g., liquefaction, tsunamis, landslides) of a Cascadia event appreciation of hearing about the various ways that researchers and practitioners are addressing Cascadia hazards from academic and emergency management perspectives
Similarities between the challenges faced by different organizations in the seismic hazard community	appreciation that shared challenges increase potential for a) collaboration across the stakeholder network and b) wide applicability of CRESCENT products
Public messaging and communication issues	clear understanding of the need for consistent, actionable, and low-jargon messaging to the general public as well as to policy makers in both the public and private sectors strong emphasis on tailoring outreach efforts to vulnerable communities surprise that over-alerting does not seem to pose as great of a concern as previously perceived
Preparedness within infrastructure and utilities sectors	understanding of the ways that utilities and other public infrastructure representatives are building earthquake resilience and developing probabilistic seismic hazard analysis (PSHA) models

	<p>realization of the differences between PSHA models used by utilities as opposed to governmental agencies and the need for consistency across sectors</p> <p>appreciation of the importance of Oregon’s Critical Energy Infrastructure (CEI) Hub in the conversation around earthquake resilience</p>
Need for diverse and interdisciplinary approaches to Cascadia hazards	appreciation of the importance of integrating the work of emergency managers, utilities engineers, legislators, and community organizers in cross-disciplinary earthquake research and practical applications of that research
Resources and funding constraints	<p>widespread concern over limited resources for investigating and preparing for seismic hazards</p> <p>appreciation of need for increased funding from state and federal sources in order to develop a comprehensive and integrated response plan for a range of disaster scenarios</p>

Table A4 – Summary of Reflection Activity prompt 2 responses	
<i>Main excitement themes</i>	<i>Specific interests</i>
Initiating and strengthening cross-organizational relationships for collaboration	<p>Common goals for continued connections, including collaborating on the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Public outreach and communication · Scientific research · Translating science products into models and tools for enhancing community resilience · Data sharing · Workforce development · Resource sharing
Enthusiasm for CRESCENT products, initiatives and their potential impact	<p>contributing to and utilizing CRESCENT’s products, particularly the CFM and CVM</p> <p>anticipation of positive workshop outcomes and a better future resulting from facilitating this kind of cross-sector collaboration</p>
Advancements in earthquake hazard science and its real world applications	<p>eagerness for parallel progress on both scientific understanding of Cascadia seismic processes and downstream hazards as well as a more nuanced approach to the societal intersections with these hazards</p> <p>interest in the development of different scenarios and the potential for future ground motion modeling and subsequent integration into public hazard communication</p>
Progress in public awareness and seismic hazard preparedness	<p>potential for the network of CRESCENT partners to facilitate the creation of consistent messaging about the seismic hazards of Cascadia for more effective public outreach</p> <p>enthusiasm for local/regional preparedness initiatives like ODART and for future coordination of preparation and response efforts across agencies and organizations</p>

A3.3 Evaluation Responses

A formal evaluation was conducted via a Qualtrics survey emailed to participants during the week following the workshop. This was completed by 53 participants. As well as questions to get feedback on efficacy of the workshop and suggestions for future iterations, the following questions were asked to augment the data gathered from the collaborative responses to the breakout session prompts:

- *What are some of the biggest challenges you face, and how could that work benefit from CRESCENT-related science?*
- *Which CRESCENT products might be applicable to you and your organization, and how would you like to interact with these products?*
- *In the context of what you’ve learned today about CRESCENT, what products/research are missing or could better serve you? (e.g., new features, refinements to existing features, changes to make things easier to use, better instructions or tutorials, etc.)*
- *How can CRESCENT best facilitate interorganizational collaboration?*

Responses are summarized in Table A5.

<i>Main challenges</i>	<i>Applicable CRESCENT products</i>	<i>Missing products/ research</i>	<i>Ideas for interorganizational collaboration</i>
<p>COMMUNICATION AND ADVOCACY</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equitable warning and preparedness planning • Effective, consistent communication of science and risk to the public and policymakers • Cross-border collaboration on science communication and resilience efforts • Balancing incorporation of new science insights while maintaining consistency of hazard information for public • Convincing elected officials of urgency of CSZ preparation 	<p>interest in products from all CRESCENT working groups, and the community fault and velocity models in particular</p> <p>interest in the ground motion special interest group’s research and downstream products</p>	<p>Suggestions included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updated inundation maps • Region specific datasets • Products in GIS format • Interactive hazard maps • Recurrence intervals for scenarios • Duration of expected cascading hazards • Early warning system research and implementations • Tsunami research and real-time forecasting • Online tools for leaning about lifeline infrastructure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • regular email newsletter, to include working group updates, and relevant projects, events and grant application deadlines. • Continued annual in-person meetings like this workshop • Work group/profession specific meetings with options for virtual attendance • Regional meetings and workshops • Contact lists, email listservs • Monthly webinars
<p>RESOURCE LIMITATIONS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One-person programs • Lack of funding and skilled scientists • Need convincing cost-benefit analysis to justify coastal mitigation projects 	<p>other valued products and services that</p>		

<p>RISK ANALYSIS AND EMERGENCY MANAGEMENT</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having scenarios and materials targeted to emergency management • Risk quantification for specific regions and infrastructure • Need scenarios to be probabilistic (quantified by a return period/range of return periods) • Tsunami evacuation and CSZ event recovery planning • Telecommunications infrastructure in PNW does not take CSZ/general seismic risks into account 	<p>CRESCENT will provide:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geoscience Education and Inclusion initiatives • Web resources and data depository • Inclusive outreach efforts • Networking opportunities • Research grants 	<p>vulnerabilities and plans for seismic updates</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dashboard for all Cascadia-related data, from detailed engineering/technical data to less technical data and summaries for emergency managers and elected officials • Scenarios • Science communication resources • A working group focused on social science research • Loss modeling • Global subduction zone studies • All ground motion modeling – not just CSZ origin • Plan for translation of science into practice • Resilience building examples/case studies • Jargon-free outreach materials • CRESCENT communications plan 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct invitation to meetings for collaboration, relationship building and updates (e.g meeting with P&A Program Manager) • “boots on the ground” relationship building, e.g. attending meetings of stakeholder organizations • Create CRESCENT “agency liaisons”, possibly by area of expertise (e.g. utilities, local jurisdictions, state, federal, tribal)
<p>RESEARCH AND DATA NEEDS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need realistic ground motion estimates for I-5 corridor and codependent infrastructure systems – consider regional earthquakes • Need more NW California specific tsunami hazard research • Rapid data gathering for active on and offshore faults throughout Cascadia • Lack of consolidated source of the varied Cascadia research, products and resources available • Accessing latest peer-reviewed scientific information and data that can feed into updating seismic hazard assessments • Science outputs need to have community/industry buy-in and standard computational and work-flow compatibility (e.g. regionalized datasets and usable data formats) 			